

WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING POLICY IN TRADE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article deals with the effective organization of marketing services in the enterprise, the reflection of the priorities of the implementation of the marketing process, the determination of the main requirements for the formation of the marketing strategy of the enterprise, the conduct of marketing research, the presentation of the main methods of market segmentation, and the introduction of an effective marketing control system.*

Keywords: *enterprise, service, marketing process, segment, competition, advertising.*

Introduction. In the conditions of the market economy, each business entity needs to develop a policy that reflects the general requirements and procedures of activity in the sales segment. Ensuring effective sales of products and services in a competitive environment requires optimal use of all methods and tools of the marketing system. Usually, a positive solution to this issue is carried out by developing an excellent marketing policy in trade and service enterprises.

Development of marketing policy is one of the main functions of the marketing service of every business entity. Also, the marketing policy determines the main tasks and obligations of the marketing service and the order of work organization.

Marketing policy in commercial enterprises is a type of document that summarizes marketing activities and ensures effective implementation of marketing strategy. In the development of marketing policy, it is necessary to be based on principles such as accuracy, truthfulness, comprehensiveness, and interrelationship.

Marketing policy is an important component of the policy of development of production and service enterprises. This policy covers internal factors such as product, sales, price and service. This structure of the marketing policy represents the main rules in the stages of selection, creation, pricing of new goods and services, and finally, sales of goods and services.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. A marketing policy should enable management to make strategic and tactical decisions that help optimize the sales process. Also, the marketing policy should be aimed at strengthening and expanding the company's position in the sales segment, increasing the profit of marketing processes, increasing the number of potential consumers, and ensuring an advantage in the competition.

The development of a set of marketing policies in sales of products and services ensures the achievement of the following strategic goals:

- effective organization of marketing service, reflection of priority directions of implementation of marketing process;
- defining the main requirements for the formation of the marketing strategy of the enterprise;
- conducting marketing research, representing the main methods of market segmentation;

- introduction of an effective marketing control system, etc.

Analysis shows that the effective development of marketing policy in trade and service enterprises largely depends on the environment in the selected sales segment. If the competitive environment in the sales segment is high, in this case, the trading company is forced to develop a communication and service policy perfectly.

Price policy is considered the main part of the company's marketing policy, and it is one of the important factors of accelerating the movement of goods in the sales market and increasing the number of consumers.

The price policy in trade enterprises is a set of measures aimed at setting the optimal price for the products on sale, ensuring price elasticity based on the analysis of the market situation.

Effective implementation of pricing policy in marketing ensures achievement of the following strategic goals:

- increasing the volume of sales by properly managing the price of products and services;
- promoting the sale of this product when the demand for a specific product or type of service decreases;
- to help reduce the level of damage that can be seen from the sale of these products when another group of goods or services competing with the product appears on the market, etc.

It is developed based on the development of the price policy in trading enterprises and the analysis of the situation in the sales market. The following methods of price policy formulation are used:

– ***on-demand routing***. In this case, the price policy is formed taking into account the price of similar or one group of goods in the market;

– ***cost-based routing***. In this way, the price policy is adapted to the goal of expanding the share in the sales segment. In this case, the main strategic goal is to increase the number of consumers by using a flexible price system;

- ***orientation towards competitors***. In this method, the price policy is intended to provide an advantage over competitors in the sales market.

The sales policy in trade enterprises is a type of document that helps to solve the problems of speeding up the movement of goods on sale, increasing the interest of consumers in the brand.

The sales policy should structurally include defining the strategic goals of enterprises in the market segment, reflecting the principles of the sales policy, classifying consumers and sales channels, the content of sales methods, describing the places of distribution of goods, and the procedure for working with suppliers and intermediaries.

In marketing, the sales policy is also important in expanding the consumer base, eliminating the negative effects of seasonal changes on the sales process, increasing the brand's competitiveness in the sales segment, and diversifying the sales segment and product range.

The sales policy represents the basic requirements for the sales process. Therefore, the sales policy in enterprises should ensure the achievement of the following strategic goals:

- strengthening the sales culture, reflecting the main requirements for the effectiveness of the sales staff;
- establishing the basic rules for regulating and controlling the activities of distribution channels of goods and services;
- development of effective sales methods;

- the quality of the goods on sale, the process of better rendering of services, improvement of the packaging procedure, introduction of a system for expanding the assortment of goods and the variety of services, etc.

It is expedient that the policy of selling goods in retail enterprises clearly expresses the rules for organizing trade relations with different categories of the population, the correct placement of sales channels, determining the aesthetic arrangement of the sales hall, and the correct selection of the system for distributing information (advertising) to consumers.

Wholesale trade enterprises, on the other hand, need to focus their sales policy on such goals as establishing profitable cooperation with distributors, expanding the sales segment, and forming a reliable logistics system.

The sales policy of trade and service enterprises should provide recommendations on which goods or services to continue selling, on which goods or services to revise pricing, and to improve the company's sales service structure. In general, the conduct of the sales policy should ensure that the goods are sold in the greatest possible quantity and at reasonable prices.

In enterprises with a large sales volume, it is appropriate to develop an assortment policy along with a sales policy. Assortment policy includes activities related to the formation of the assortment of goods and services on sale based on market needs. Especially in retail marketing, the assortment policy is an important tool in systematically meeting the needs of the target consumer group. This policy makes it possible to update the composition of goods on sale and the quality of services, to organize the sales process in accordance with the needs of the consumer layer in the sales segment.

Also, the assortment policy appears as a factor that optimizes the risk of operating at a loss for trade and service enterprises, and helps to increase the number of customers in a competitive environment.

Usually, communication policy is used as an important factor to accelerate the movement of goods in sales segments with a high competitive environment. Communication policy reflects the main directions of movement of goods in the market.

Communication in the service of marketing represents the process of establishing mutually beneficial relations between trade and service enterprises with suppliers and consumers, as well as the rapid exchange of necessary information.

The following strategic goals are aimed at developing a communication policy in marketing:

- to increase the perception of consumers regarding the products or services that are intended for sale and presentation, to reveal the positive features of new goods and services;
- use of sales promotion methods, introduction of a mechanism to increase the level of service to consumers;
- working with potential buyers, including determining the procedure for studying the requirements and complaints of buyers regarding the quality and design of the goods on sale;
- revitalizing the trade of goods and services that could not withstand competition, minimizing the losses that the enterprise may suffer from the sale of these goods, etc.

In this concept, means of marketing communication represent the process of mutually supporting each other. This is a reliable guarantee of maintaining a brand and a constant group of consumers in a competitive environment

In our opinion, the application of an integrated communication policy in marketing provides the following advantages:

- achieving effective marketing management in accelerating the movement of goods;
- establishing long-term cooperative relations with a wide group of consumers, potential suppliers and intermediaries;
- getting as accurate pricing as possible of the situation in the sales segment, etc.

At the same time, the process of developing an integrated communication policy is labor-intensive, and it is necessary to develop high-quality skills in this process. In the development of this policy, trading entities with a high share in the sales market will have more opportunities due to sufficient financial resources.

Service policy in trade marketing is a set of measures to facilitate the sales process and create additional convenience for consumers in the sales process. The development of the service policy will have a positive effect on the activities of wholesale trade entities that sell large quantities, and large retail complexes.

The service policy defines the terms of delivery of goods to consumers or points of sale, the functions of the departments responsible for this process.

In short, it is appropriate to pay close attention to the following aspects when developing a marketing policy in trade and service enterprises;

- raising the marketing policy not only as a set of procedures expressed on paper, but to the level of a conceptual basis aimed at increasing the efficiency of marketing processes, which in turn allows increasing the responsibility of marketing service employees;
- involvement of qualified marketing team in development of marketing policy;
- close coordination of marketing policy with the activities of other divisions of the enterprise;
- in order to coordinate the marketing policy, to establish personnel training not only in the "Marketing" specialty, but also in the "Sales officer" specialty in higher educational institutions.

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